

HERPHÆSTUS

Heritage in Europe: new technologies in craft for preserving and innovating futures

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Report on the vision think tank

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Table of Contents

1.0 Definition of a Think Tank	7
1.0.1 Think tanks as drivers of innovation	7
1.1 Defining the HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank	8
1.1.1 Building Upon Maker’s Island Bornholm	9
1.1.2 The Role of BOFA	9
1.1.3 A Resilient, Long-Term Network.....	9
2.0 From Maker’s Island to the HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank	11
2.1 Maker’s Island and its Role in the EU Horizon Project HEPHAESTUS	11
2.1.1 Stakeholders and Key Organizations	12
2.1.2 Historical context of Maker’s Island	12
2.1.3 Maker’s Island at a Crossroads	16
2.2 Synergies with HEPHAESTUS WP1 and WP3	18
2.2.1 Synergies to T1.3.....	18
2.2.2 Synergies to T3.1.....	21
3.0 Organizing the HEPHAESTUS Think Tank	23
3.1 The HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank Going Forward	23
3.1.1 Maker’s Island and the Formation of a Think Tank within the HEPHAESTUS Project	23
3.1.2 A Collaborative Think Tank for Innovation in Craft and Sustainability	23
3.1.3 Core Objectives of the Think Tank	23
3.1.4 Collaborative Structure and Network Governance	24
3.1.5 Interdisciplinary Collaboration and Long-Term Vision	24
3.1.6 Outputs and Next Steps	24
3.2 The Bassano Ecosystem and its contribution to the Vision Think Tank	25
3.2.1 Business Models for Craft Makers.....	26
3.2.2 Think Tank and HGLL Synergies	26
4.0 Towards a Road Map for Circular Economy	27
4.0.1 Focus Areas and Approaches	27
4.0.2 Structure and Timeline	27
4.0.3 Living Document for Present Realities.....	28
References	29

List of table and figures

Figures and Tables	Page #
Figure 1. Relationship between the HEPHAESTUS Think Tank, Maker's Island, and the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (HGLL). Own Elaboration.	9
Figure 2. Christina Schou Christensen (CSC Keramik/Dansk Kaolin) develops glazes using recycled surplus materials. Photos: Kasper Agergaard (ceramic test materials); Bo Johannsen (portrait of Christina Schou Christensen). Source: Business Center Bornholm (n.d.).	19
Figure 3: Extended business model for Christina Schou	20
Figure 4. Craft makers, researchers, and local stakeholders in dialogue during the HEPHAESTUS co-creation workshop on Bornholm (September 2024). Photo: HEPHAESTUS Project (2024).	21
Figure 5: Visualization of the Bassano stakeholder support structure	25

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
ACAB	Arts and Crafts Association Bornholm
BCB	Business Center Bornholm
BOFA	Bornholm's Waste Management Authority
HGLL	HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab
EBBU	Erhvervs-, Bolig- og Beskæftigelsesudvalget (Economic, Business, & Planning Committee)

1.0 Definition of a Think Tank

The concept of think tanks has evolved significantly since their inception, primarily regarding their roles and definitions across various academic disciplines. In policy studies, think tanks are primarily viewed as non-profit organizations dedicated to producing research aimed at informing public policy debates. Jezierska (2020) highlights the absence of a definitive characterization of think tanks, noting their engagement in policy advice and their independence from government entities. This lack of consensus complicates their classification and the clarity of their influence on policymaking. Pautz (2011) underscores the functional aspects of think tanks, recommending a shift away from rigid organizational definitions towards understanding their operational roles and contributions to policy discourse. This approach resonates with the notion that think tanks operate within a complex interaction of interests, expertise, and power dynamics (Pautz, 2020). According to Tian (2018) think tanks contribute to the provision of policy alternatives and cultivating a pool of expert talent. Similarly, Ahmad (2008) depicts think tanks as vital agents that frame policy discussions and provide essential analyses, particularly in the contextual landscape of U.S. governance, where their influence has grown markedly since the early twentieth century. The Danish landscape also reflects this diversity, with think tanks ranging from publicly funded advisory bodies to more media-visible policy entrepreneurs. For instance, CONCITO has emerged as a key actor in climate and sustainability policy, positioning itself as a knowledge broker across political and sectoral lines (Kelstrup & Blach-Ørsten, 2020). In contrast, the controversy surrounding Bjørn Lomborg's former think tank, the Environmental Assessment Institute, illustrates how think tanks can also become flashpoints in political and scientific debates, particularly when visibility and governmental ties complicate perceptions of neutrality and credibility (Jamison, 2004; van den Bergh, 2010).

In the European Union (EU), think tanks play a significant and multifaceted role in the policy-making process, reflecting the distinct governance structures and political context of the region. Primarily, they serve as knowledge intermediaries, conducting research and analysis that inform policymakers at various levels, including EU institutions, member states, and local governments. In this respect think tanks are considered particularly useful in addressing complex cross-border challenges such as climate change, economic integration, and security (Jezierska, 2020; Tian, 2018). Unlike their counterparts in the United States, EU think tanks often emphasize collaboration and consensus-building due to the multi-layered governance framework of the EU, which necessitates the integration of diverse stakeholder perspectives (Ahmad, 2008; Rashid, 2013).

Furthermore, think tanks in the EU contribute to public discourse by nurturing informed debate among civil society and the electorate, aiming to enhance transparency and democratic legitimacy within EU governance (Pautz, 2011; Pautz, 2020). The EU's unique context encourages think tanks to bridge the gap between the political elite and the general populace, promoting participatory governance approaches (Wellstead & Howlett, 2021; Plehwe, 2021). However, the ideological breadth of EU think tanks is notably wider than in the U.S., resulting in more diverse political viewpoints coexisting and contributing to policy discussions—from neoliberal to social democratic (Smith et al., 2013). In summary, think tanks in the EU not only inform policy through research but also facilitate democratic engagement and dialogue within a complex political landscape, setting them apart from the typically more partisan-focused think tanks observed in the U.S.

1.0.1 Think tanks as drivers of innovation

The role of think tanks has been redefined and expanded towards a recognition of think tanks as stimuli for innovation. Wellstead & Howlett (2021) advocate for a re-evaluation of traditional concepts of think tanks, particularly in the context of emerging knowledge-based policy organizations such as innovation labs and behaviorally driven policy units. These "new" think tanks incorporate characteristics of classic think tanks but possess distinct orientations that prioritize innovative approaches to public policy challenges. The growth of quasi-independent organizations, which sometimes blur the lines between state apparatus and independent research entities, highlights the necessity of clearly demarcating the roles of think tanks in fostering public sector innovation. Rashid Rashid (2013) points to the dynamic spectrum of think tanks that operate not only independently but also in coordination with government efforts, thus contributing to a more robust dialogue around innovation in policy processes. By situating themselves as intermediaries, these organizations amplify the generation of knowledge and integration of a range of policy perspectives, facilitating collaborative forms of innovation (Plehwe, 2021; Smith et al., 2013). Moreover, as shown by Fraussen and Pattyn (2023), think tanks have increasingly become embedded in consensus-seeking advisory systems that highlight their evolving nature and capacity to drive innovation within public policymaking frameworks. This transformation reflects a growing awareness of the need for integrated approaches to policy challenges that leverage research and innovative practices from different stakeholders.

1.1 Defining the HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank

The HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank is a collaborative, network-based platform designed to support innovation and policy development across the craft and sustainability sectors. It connects practitioners, institutions, and researchers in order to translate local knowledge – especially from the craft sector – into cross-sectoral strategies, experimental pilots, and evidence-based policy insights.

As shown in Figure 1, the Think Tank acts as a space where craft makers, Arts and Crafts Association Bornholm (ACAB), the Royal Danish Academy, and other stakeholders exchange ideas, articulate needs, and collaborate on shared initiatives. Rather than replacing Bornholm's Maker's Island platform – which is nearing potential decommissioning (see Section 2.1.3) - the Think Tank builds on its legacy while offering a more flexible, distributed model for coordination.

Positioned alongside the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (HGLL), the Think Tank plays a bridging role: it gathers insight into lived experiences within the craft ecosystem and feeds these into Living Lab experimentation. In return, the Think Tank also helps preserve and apply the insights, practices, and methods developed through HGLL activities, ensuring their continuity beyond the lifespan of the HEPHAESTUS project.

Unlike traditional, top-down think tanks, the HEPHAESTUS model prioritizes bottom-up engagement, lightweight structure, and local adaptability. Its activities include shared learning, cross-partner working groups, and issue-based collaboration in areas such as sustainable materials, skills development, tourism, and circular economy transitions. These efforts reflect growing EU-level interest in innovation-oriented, deliberative think tanks that combine democratic engagement with practical experimentation (Jeziarska, 2020; Fraussen & Pattyn, 2023; Wellstead & Howlett, 2021).

Figure 1. Relationship between the HEPHAESTUS Think Tank, Maker’s Island, and the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab (HGLL). Own Elaboration.

1.1.1 Building Upon Maker’s Island Bornholm

To ground its work in an existing support structure, the Think Tank builds on the experiences, networks, and facilities of Maker’s Island Bornholm. As an established entity focused on craft promotion, Maker’s Island offers a ready-made community, event infrastructure, and set of working groups that the Think Tank can tap into. This is especially relevant in the face of uncertain municipal or political support for Maker’s Island: the Think Tank can work pragmatically within these evolving conditions by mobilizing ad hoc partnerships and leveraging the expertise of different stakeholders.

1.1.2 The Role of BOFA

Bornholm’s waste management authority, BOFA, assumes a distinctive part within the Think Tank’s broader vision. Having led the HGLL activities and having actively collaborated with local craft makers from the ground up, BOFA injects a crucial sustainability perspective in the local craft ecosystem that is increasingly interested in it (Sparre-Petersen, 2014; Sparre-Petersen, 2017). Their focus on circular waste management and local resource flows (BOFA, 2019; Christensen, Hjul-Nielsen, Moalem & Johansen, 2021; BOFA, 2022; Hjul-Nielsen, Santos, Christensen & Andrade, 2023; Moalem, Nørup, Ghosh & Sastre, 2024) complements the more traditional craft and tourism interests, thereby enriching the Think Tank’s capacity to address environmental challenges and strengthen trust among local craft makers.

1.1.3 A Resilient, Long-Term Network

Beyond fostering short-term dialogue, the Think Tank is conceived as a resilient organizational (or inter-organizational) infrastructure that can thrive despite political ebbs and flows. Its governance

structure is intentionally flexible, enabling cross-sector collaborations to persist even when specific funding lines or municipal mandates change. By integrating diverse stakeholder groups—including craft makers, academic institutions, NGOs, and public authorities—the Think Tank aspires to coordinate sustainable craft development on Bornholm and, by extension, in other regions facing similar challenges.

Ultimately, the HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank seeks to become a shared knowledge repository, a driver of craft-focused innovation, and a catalyst for sustainable policy. In doing so, it not only extends the impact of the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab but also ensures that Bornholm’s unique craft ecosystem continues to evolve, adapt, and flourish in the years to come.

2.0 From Maker’s Island to the HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank

This chapter introduces the background, motivations, and strategic transition from Maker’s Island Bornholm to the proposed HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank. Drawing on the foundations laid during the Maker’s Island initiative (2019–2024), this section traces how a locally anchored craft development platform evolved into a multi-stakeholder ecosystem primed for policy innovation and circular economy transformation.

Bornholm’s designation as a World Craft Region in 2017 catalyzed a series of place-based interventions under the Maker’s Island banner, aligning craft development with economic renewal, cultural identity, and sustainability. Over the course of five years, the Maker’s Island framework demonstrated measurable impact in areas such as employment growth, sector visibility, and inter-institutional collaboration. As outlined in subsequent sections, these achievements were underpinned by coordinated efforts between municipal actors, craft organizations, museums, and academic institutions.

However, as the formal municipal support for Maker’s Island began to sunset in 2024, local stakeholders were faced with a critical juncture: how to preserve and expand the collaborative momentum without a centralized coordinating structure. It is within this context that the idea of a Vision Think Tank was developed—an initiative grounded in the lived experience of Maker’s Island but geared toward future-oriented, systemic policy engagement.

The following sections document this transition in detail. Section 2.1 offers a chronological and contextual account of the Maker’s Island initiative, its stakeholders, and its achievements, while also exploring the political and institutional conditions that led to its potential discontinuation. Section 2.2 highlights how the lessons and synergies from Maker’s Island have informed the preliminary establishment of the HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank, particularly in connection with Work Packages 1 and 3.

By capturing this institutional and narrative arc – from local coordination platform to distributed policy engine – this chapter situates the Think Tank as a continuity mechanism for circular innovation and craft sector sustainability on Bornholm, and as a replicable governance model for other regions.

2.1 Maker’s Island and its Role in the EU Horizon Project HEPHAESTUS

Section 2.1 provides a grounded account of how Maker’s Island was operationalized through a series of structured partnerships and phased municipal support. This section focuses on the initiative’s institutional architecture, yearly milestones, and evolving modes of coordination. It introduces the main stakeholder organizations involved in shaping Bornholm’s craft ecosystem, and lays the groundwork for understanding how this platform now informs the development of the HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank.

2.1.1 Stakeholders and Key Organizations

Maker's Island Bornholm plays a pivotal role in the HEPHAESTUS project by integrating traditional craftsmanship with cutting-edge technology and sustainability. The initiative brings together diverse stakeholders, including governmental bodies, business organizations, educational institutions, and cultural associations, all working towards fostering innovation and a circular economy in the craft sector.

Key stakeholders include:

- **Regional Municipality of Bornholm (BRK)** – Provides political and administrative leadership, ensuring local policies align with the project's objectives.
- **Bornholm's Waste Management (BOFA)** – Leads the HEPHAESTUS Green Living Lab, pioneering waste-free circular business models within crafts.
- **Arts and Crafts Association Bornholm (ACAB)** – Represents artisans and facilitates professional networking, exhibitions, and skill development.
- **Bornholms Museum and Hjorths Fabrik** – Contribute expertise in cultural heritage preservation, connecting historical craft practices with modern innovations.
- **Royal Danish Academy, Bornholm** – Engages in research and education, fostering talent and new methodologies in craft industries.
- **Bornholm's Center for Arts and Crafts at Grønbechs Gård** – Acts as a hub for exhibitions, workshops, and international craft collaborations.
- **Destination Bornholm** – Supports tourism-related initiatives, ensuring the craft sector remains an integral part of Bornholm's cultural identity and visitor economy.
- **Business Center Bornholm** – Facilitates local business development, helping craft enterprises adapt to new economic models.

2.1.2 Historical context of Maker's Island

Below is a comprehensive year-by-year consolidation of how the Maker's Island Bornholm initiative took shape, advanced, and ultimately wrapped up its 2020–2022 cycle, along with a look toward the 2023–2025 extension. This write-up blends a conventional chronological format with key bullet points for clarity, drawing on the appended documents from 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, and 2024.

The Emergence of Maker's Island Bornholm

In 2017, Bornholm's designation as a World Craft Region functioned much like a "Michelin star" for the island's artisans, signaling quality and prestige on an international scale. Energized by this distinction, local stakeholders—from municipal officials to craft makers and tourism professionals—saw a chance to boost economic growth, strengthen Bornholm's year-round appeal, and spotlight its rich traditions in ceramics, glass, textiles, and beyond. Early on, they identified four interlinked priorities: to elevate public awareness of Bornholm's craft ecosystem, to foster tighter coordination among artisans and allied sectors, to enhance professional competencies in areas such as marketing and scaling, and to facilitate commercialization through exports, experiential tourism, and broader collaborations.

These ambitions soon coalesced into a more structured initiative called *Maker's Island Bornholm*, guided by a municipal steering group. In the sections that follow, a chronological overview illustrates how each subsequent year built on earlier successes, ultimately leading to an expanded plan for 2023–2025.

2019: Launching the World Craft Region Effort

In 2019, buoyed by Bornholm's recent status as a World Craft Region, local stakeholders—most prominently Arts and Crafts Association Bornholm (ACAB)—petitioned the municipality for financial support to develop a robust business framework around the island's craft heritage. Municipal documents likened this designation to earning the “Michelin star of the craft world,” highlighting the economic promise tied to Bornholm's ceramics, glass, and other handmade traditions (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2019a). Although the steering group originally requested 750,000 DKK per year (2019–2021) to fund commercialization, coordination, and competence development, the municipality settled on an initial allocation of 500,000 DKK for a 12-month period (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2019a).

Even at this preliminary stage, boosting off-season tourism, attracting new talent, and increasing craft-sector turnover were key objectives (Broegaard & Andersen, 2018; Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2019b). By late 2019, stakeholders were notably optimistic: new figures from ACAB showed approximately 28 million DKK in annual turnover among its members. As a result, momentum built around a plan to unify promotional efforts, strengthen artisan skill sets, and position Bornholm as a compelling destination for craft enthusiasts year-round.

2020: Maker's Island Bornholm Project Formally Approved

In 2020, the initiative adopted its now-official name – Maker's Island Bornholm – and secured a defined operational period from 1 May 2020 to 31 December 2022 (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2020a). Built on the momentum of the World Craft Region title, the project was anchored by four strategic pillars – Commercialization, Competence Development, Communication, and Coordination – designed to grow the craft sector through commercialization, professional training, marketing, and cross-sector collaboration (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2020b).

The Economic, Business, and Planning Committee (ØEPU) approved 2.2 million DKK from its subsidy pool, conditional on external co-financing that would raise the total project budget to approximately 5 million DKK (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2020a). Drawing on projections from earlier CRT reports, the steering group estimated that the project could generate a sector-wide turnover increase of up to 46.6 million DKK over three years, linked to professionalization, tourism growth, and increased talent attraction (Broegaard & Andersen, 2018; Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2020b).

By the end of 2020, the initiative had launched the Bornholm Craft Collection, completed the first round of business training for 18 enterprises, and formed partnerships with ACAB, the municipality, and institutions such as Hjorths Fabrik and Destination Bornholm (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2020c; 2020d). These actions were supported by a clear timeline and communications plan, which included digital visibility, international promotion, and enhanced coordination—laying the groundwork for increased brand recognition and new market access within the global craft community (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2020e; 2020f).

2021: Status Update and a Revised Steering Group

By the beginning of 2021, Maker's Island Bornholm was showing promising signs of progress, even as the COVID-19 pandemic delayed some components and tempered expectations for international exchange (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2021a). In February, the *Økonomi-, Erhvervs- og Planudvalget* (municipal council subcommittee) approved a revised project charter, which included structural changes to the steering group and a reallocation of the project coordinator role into the Maker's Island budget—replacing the prior part-time municipal staff arrangement (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2021a; 2021b).

These changes formalized the governance framework, introducing clearer representation for stakeholders such as Arts and Crafts Association Bornholm (ACAB) and replacing director-specific seats with general institutional representatives. The strategic plan emphasized long-term value creation through coordination, communication, commercialization, and competence development (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2021c).

Throughout 2021, the project advanced through targeted partnerships with Destination Bornholm, Business Center Bornholm, and other regional players. Joint efforts promoted immersive craft experiences, launched seasonal events, and reinforced Bornholm's positioning as a year-round destination (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2021a; 2021d). Maker's Island also provided capacity-building workshops in branding and finance, supporting both emerging and established artisans.

By year's end, Maker's Island had evolved into a more cohesive platform, coordinating cross-sector activities while preparing for future funding rounds. Public documents highlighted its role in boosting off-season tourism and attracting new talent, pointing to a sharpened ambition to use Bornholm's craft identity as an engine for regional economic renewal (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2021c; 2021e).

2022: Midterm Evaluation—Strong Growth and a New Festival

By 2022, a midterm evaluation painted a highly encouraging picture of Bornholm's craft sector. Between 2017 and 2020, participating craft businesses achieved an average annual turnover increase of 20%, exceeding Maker's Island's original goal of 17% per year (Broegaard & Hedetoft, 2022). This growth aligned with a surge in new enterprise formation—particularly among younger artisans working in ceramics—and deeper collaboration across tourism and business sectors (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2022a; Broegaard & Hedetoft, 2022).

A key milestone during this period was the successful launch of Bornholm Craft Weeks (September–October 2021), a six-week autumn festival involving over 70 local craft businesses and 65 unique events. The festival aimed to extend the tourist season while showcasing Bornholm's cultural and artisanal identity. Evaluation results indicate it was well-received by artisans and visitors alike, and is now considered a potential flagship initiative for the Maker's Island strategy going forward (Broegaard & Hedetoft, 2022).

The evaluation also credited the Maker's Island secretariat with playing a pivotal coordinating role: helping micro-enterprises secure funding, promoting synergy among stakeholders, and organizing professional development opportunities, such as marketing workshops and guided press events with Destination Bornholm (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2022a; 2022b). These efforts were essential in amplifying Bornholm's visibility as a "World Craft Region" and building the groundwork for further strategic development.

Encouraged by the results, the steering group began planning the 2023–2025 phase. Recognizing that sustained, multi-year funding would be critical for preserving momentum, they called for continued support and positioned craft development as a central pillar of Bornholm’s broader economic and place-branding strategy (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2022a).

2024: Final Wrap-Up for 2020–2022 and a New Funding Phase

In the final accounting for the 2020–2022 period, Maker’s Island Bornholm utilized approximately 1.58 million DKK of the originally allocated 2.2 million DKK from the municipality, leaving a surplus of 619,322 DKK in unused funds. However, a deficit of 298,827 DKK appeared in the project’s accounts due to two main factors: the cancellation of the Bornholm Craft Collection initiative, and the fact that certain Landdistriktspulje funds were paid directly to ACAB instead of flowing through Bornholm Regional Municipality (BRK), thus reducing the eligible reimbursement amount (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2024a). To resolve the discrepancy, the municipal EBBU subcommittee approved a reallocation of 298,827 DKK from the remaining municipal grant to balance the accounts (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2024a).

The final evaluation praised the overall project execution, noting that Maker’s Island met or exceeded many of its goals. Income among Bornholm’s craft sector grew by 26% from 2019 to 2022, and employment in the sector rose by 31% between 2017 and 2022—figures that outpaced trends both locally and nationally (Broegaard & Hedetoft, 2023). Visibility also surged, with international press coverage of Bornholm’s crafts increasing fiftyfold during the same period (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2024b).

Among the noteworthy funders of the upcoming phase was the HEPHAESTUS project (via BOFA), which contributed a combined 239,000 DKK across 2024 and 2025 to support sustainable innovation and interdisciplinary collaboration within the craft sector (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2024c).

Despite robust results and an extended funding ecosystem, the structure of the 2023–2025 grant model proved challenging. Several foundations declined to fund Maker’s Island due to the conditionality of its municipal support. Still, in August 2024, the municipality confirmed retention of the 600,000 DKK earmarked for 2025, acknowledging the continued importance of the project (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2024b).

From its modest 2019 pilot to the closeout of its 2020–2022 cycle and the launch of a new 2023–2025 phase, Maker’s Island Bornholm has shown how a place-based craft initiative can deliver measurable results when supported by strategic planning and public funding. Grounded in the World Craft Region designation, the project advanced through four recurring pillars—commercialization, competence development, communication, and coordination—adopted in various forms across municipal frameworks and steering documents (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2020b; 2021c).

Even with the delays and adjustments brought on by the COVID-19 pandemic and the non-realization of the Bornholm Craft Collection subproject, the initiative met or exceeded many of its key goals. Midterm and final evaluations recorded a 26% rise in income and a 31% growth in employment within the craft sector between 2017 and 2022, alongside a significant increase in younger maker arrivals and expanded collaborations in tourism and education (Broegaard & Hedetoft, 2022, 2023). Signature achievements such as Bornholm Craft Weeks helped boost visibility and extend the visitor season, while enhanced internal coordination enabled more efficient marketing and training support for small craft businesses (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2022b; 2024b).

By 2024, the original 2020–2022 period was formally concluded with a reconciled budget and lessons learned regarding municipal versus external fund administration (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2024a). The new 2023–2025 cycle emphasizes co-financing and stakeholder matching, drawing in partners like BOFA and the HEPHAESTUS project, whose funding supports sustainability-oriented innovation at the intersection of craft and community development (Regional Municipality of Bornholm, 2024c).

What began as a response to international recognition has since grown into a multi-sector collaboration model with a long-term outlook. Rather than simply a badge of honor, the World Craft Region status now serves as an operational framework for linking cultural heritage to economic opportunity – across seasons, sectors, and generations.

2.1.3 Maker’s Island at a Crossroads

Maker’s Island Bornholm has fostered a uniquely collaborative environment since its inception in 2019, building on the island’s 2017 designation as a World Craft Region. Over the past six years, the Maker’s Island secretariat and steering committee have actively mobilized this prestigious title to enhance the craft sector’s visibility and impact. Key partners in this effort include the Royal Danish Academy, Arts and Crafts Association Bornholm (ACAB), Bornholms Kunstmuseum, Hjorths Fabrik, Grønbechs Gård – Bornholms Center for Kunsthåndværk, Destination Bornholm, Business Center Bornholm (BCB), and Bornholm Regional Municipality. By aligning municipal support with strategic goals in communication, coordination, commercialization, and competence development, Maker’s Island has served as a powerful springboard for year-round cultural and economic growth.

Yet as we head further into 2025, Maker’s Island faces potential decommissioning due to budget constraints and shifting political agendas. Even though upcoming events—such as Craft Weeks 2025—remain on the calendar, the future of a unified Maker’s Island structure is uncertain. Competing municipal priorities may draw funding away from craft initiatives, and the absence of a dedicated secretariat could weaken the current synergy among stakeholders. Despite its success in positioning Bornholm as a vibrant craft hub, the steering committee recognizes that other politically resonant projects may take precedence, making it challenging to secure the financial resources needed to sustain Maker’s Island in its current form.

This turning point has led the steering committee to explore various contingency plans. Their core concern is that, without a stable, overarching entity to coordinate activities, critical updates and shared resources may not flow evenly across the craft network. Some stakeholders and craft makers have described this scenario as risking fragmentation: collaborative outcomes might still be produced by separate working groups, but broader alignment on strategy, communication, and resource sharing could wane over time. In addition, certain craft makers have expressed frustration over being consulted too late in the project cycle, receiving insufficient compensation for their efforts, and lacking a clear line of sight into how decisions are made.

Nevertheless, Maker’s Island has nurtured a diverse stakeholder ecosystem that may serve as the backbone for the newly envisioned HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank. Institutions like Destination Bornholm and Business Center Bornholm have cultivated a deep understanding of the island’s cultural tourism and business-development needs, respectively. The Royal Danish Academy and ACAB have maintained vibrant relationships with the island’s craft community, while local museums, cultural centres, and municipal offices have each contributed valuable knowledge about Bornholm’s heritage and administrative frameworks. This collective experience forms a solid bedrock for any

future entity—such as the HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank—aiming to advance craft-focused initiatives that balance tradition with innovation and place-making.

From the perspective of Bornholm’s waste management authority (BOFA), the opportunity to partner with Maker’s Island arose from a shared ambition to promote sustainability and circularity in the craft sector. By spearheading the “*Bornholm without Waste 2032*” vision (BOFA, 2019), BOFA realized that integrating craft makers could accelerate the island’s transition to closed-loop material flows. This bottom-up engagement with local artisans revealed synergies in reusing and repurposing materials, shifting production processes toward zero-waste targets, and developing new revenue streams linked to circular design. These lessons—combined with Maker’s Island’s extensive craft networks—now motivate the constitution of the HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank as a vehicle for shaping a robust circular-economy roadmap that draws on both policy research and grassroots innovations.

In light of these factors, the committee and associated stakeholders have begun reorganizing around cross-partner working groups that can independently steer various initiatives if Maker’s Island is decommissioned. While these groups may preserve some of the practical functions—such as marketing, knowledge exchange, and joint events—that the secretariat once managed, questions remain about whether they can fully replicate the unifying influence and collective agenda-setting that Maker’s Island originally provided. It is precisely this gap that the Think Tank seeks to address: by consolidating the knowledge, stakeholder relationships, and collaborative ethos developed under Maker’s Island, the Think Tank aims to continue promoting Bornholm’s craft excellence—now through a circular-economy lens—long after 2025.

While Maker’s Island Bornholm has achieved measurable success in expanding Bornholm’s craft ecosystem, some concerns have emerged—primarily around communication practices and inclusion. In informal conversations with a small number of local craft makers, worries were raised that HEPHAESTUS might mirror certain challenges encountered during the Maker’s Island period, particularly in relation to timely engagement and transparent communication. These individuals reported being consulted at short notice, leaving little opportunity to influence decisions or understand the overarching rationale of new initiatives.

Although these views represent a limited sample, the perceived late-stage involvement has reportedly weakened trust for some artisans. This concern is magnified in cases where voluntary steering committee participation involves uncompensated time. However, internal correspondence indicates that at least one committee member has received partial compensation since approximately 2021—a decision made by the group itself (internal email communication, March 24, 2025).

Broader evaluations, including the 2022 midterm and 2023 final reports, portray a more balanced picture. Coordination around events such as Craft Weeks was generally rated positively by participants in formal feedback rounds, and collaboration within the ecosystem was cited as a core strength of the initiative (Broegaard & Hedetoft, 2022, 2023). Even so, communication has periodically been flagged as a weakness in internal documents, particularly when key logistical details did not reach the wider community in a timely manner.

Within ACAB, perspectives continue to vary. Some members favor deeper political engagement for craft makers, while others prefer to concentrate on their artistic practice. This diversity of views underscores the importance of carefully designed engagement strategies.

For example, the scheduling of children-focused activities during the 2024 Craft Weeks – which took place during the middle of a school term rather than over autumn break – was highlighted as a missed opportunity in one informal conversation. Though minor, such missteps reflect the broader need for inclusive planning and early input from affected participants.

As of early 2025, with the possibility that Maker’s Island might be decommissioned by mid-year, its secretariat and steering group are exploring alternative organizational formats. These include forming cross-partner working groups to continue key activities such as event marketing and skills development. While such networks may preserve continuity in practice, the lack of a central coordinating body could pose risks to long-term strategic coherence.

In this context, the HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank is well-positioned to learn from past experience. By working closely with stakeholders such as ACAB, BOFA, Destination Bornholm, and the Royal Danish Academy, it may be able to address longstanding coordination gaps. Crucially, early and meaningful engagement—not just logistical involvement—should remain a central commitment. Such a shift could help ensure that grassroots creativity is better aligned with policy agendas and that Bornholm’s craft sector continues to thrive amid institutional transitions.

2.2 Synergies with HEPHAESTUS WP1 and WP3

While the Maker’s Island initiative provided a concrete local platform for coordination and experimentation, its integration into the broader HEPHAESTUS project has allowed for cross-pollination with other Work Packages. Section 2.2 highlights the synergies between the emerging Vision Think Tank and key activities in WP1 and WP3. These interactions have enriched both the conceptual development and practical scope of the Think Tank – whether through business model innovation (T1.3), speculative futures thinking (T3.1), or localized co-creation activities under WP5. What follows is an overview of how specific project tasks have fed directly into the roadmap for a circular craft economy, grounded in Bornholm’s ecosystem but with relevance beyond.

2.2.1 Synergies to T1.3

The vision think tank actively synergized with the activities in Task 1.3 (T1.3). This task focuses on the Co-creation of new business models and business plans for sustainable craft.

The two-day co-creation workshop held at the HGLL (WP5) on Bornholm in September 2024, see Deliverable 5.2 (D5.2) provided a platform for dialogue between five craft makers from the Bornholm ecosystem. This workshop facilitated in-depth discussions around business model innovation, sustainability, needs, and challenges, aligning with the objectives of T1.3, which focuses on the co-creation of new business models and business plans for sustainable craft.

The findings from T4.1, and D4.1, which identified the educational gaps among craft makers, indicated a significant lack of basic business skills within this demographic. This gap presented an opportunity to further investigate the business models currently employed within the craft sector, as well as to explore potential innovations. Comparative research conducted in ecosystems such as Bassano (Objective 1.1; T6.2) and Bornholm allowed for a deeper understanding of existing business models in the craft sector while also integrating sustainability into the analysis. This exploration of business models in diverse contexts provided valuable insights into the challenges, financial approaches, and sustainable practices currently shaping the craft sector.

A particularly relevant case study that emerged from this investigation was that of Christina Schou, a craft maker from the Bornholm ecosystem, whose business model transformation demonstrates the intersection of technology, sustainability, and innovation within the craft sector, see Figure 2. Christina's integration of a crushing machine to produce experimental glazes from waste materials exemplifies how craft businesses can innovate by adopting new technologies and creating sustainable products. This case is indicative of the potential for craft makers to adapt and diversify their business models in response to both market demands and sustainability imperatives.

Figure 2. Christina Schou Christensen (CSC Keramik/Dansk Kaolin) develops glazes using recycled surplus materials. Photos: Kasper Agergaard (ceramic test materials); Bo Johannsen (portrait of Christina Schou Christensen). Source: Business Center Bornholm (n.d.).

The exploration of Christina's business model was undertaken by Margot Bustamente, a contributor to the HEPHAESTUS project and affiliated with CBS. The case study is based on primary data collected from a one-hour interview with Christina, supplemented by exploratory fieldwork on Bornholm over the course of nearly one month. Margot's fieldwork began with interviews with key figures in Bornholm's craft network, including Head of Secretariat at Maker's Island, and various ceramists in the Bornholm craft ecosystem including Heidi Bach, Rick Gerner, and Anna Maria Sand Jensen. These preliminary conversations revealed recurring themes, particularly the increasing use of crushing machines as a technological innovation within the local craft sector, a tool central to Christina's evolving business model.

The formal interview with Christina focused specifically on the mechanics of her business model and the ways in which she integrated new technologies into her craft practices. The collected data was subjected to a thematic coding process in three stages: the first two rounds identified emerging patterns and themes, while the third round utilized the Critical Capabilities framework (Achtenhagen et al., 2013) to evaluate Christina's actions within a broader strategic context. This methodological approach provided a robust analytical lens through which Christina's business model could be categorized, while also offering new insights that transcended the critical Capabilities framework's boundaries.

The case study's findings were further explored in relation to flexible business model concepts (Cavalcante et al., 2011), particularly in the context of Christina's extension into the production of experimental glazes. This analysis revealed how her business model has adapted to incorporate

sustainable innovation, offering a valuable model for other craft makers seeking to align their practices with environmental responsibility (see Figure 3). Public coverage and institutional recognition have reinforced the relevance of her work: TV2 Bornholm highlighted her experimentation with crushing machines to repurpose discarded materials into glazes—an approach that not only reduces waste but opens creative opportunities for product differentiation (TV2 Bornholm, 2022). Likewise, Business Center Bornholm has presented her project as a local case of circular economy in action, emphasizing its role in inspiring other craft businesses to rethink production processes, reduce resource dependency, and integrate circular design principles into their core business models (Business Center Bornholm, n.d.).

Figure 3: Extended business model for Christina Schou

The synergies identified with T1.3 directly contribute to the establishment of the vision think tank, which engages craft ambassadors in shaping the circular economy (Objective 5.4). Margot’s case study provided crucial insights that not only informed the co-creation workshop but also guided discussions on the role of technological innovation, sustainability, and flexibility in shaping future craft business models. These insights also helped deepen the understanding of the challenges craft makers face, particularly in relation to the adoption of technology and its impact on the broader ecosystem. From this case study, direct contribution to the roadmap on creating a sustainable circular economy through craft has emerged. The workshop itself specifically addressed how craft makers can overcome challenges such as sourcing packaging materials, improving production routines, and scaling their businesses in a sustainable way, see Figure 4. Additionally, discussions explored defining customer segments, developing value propositions, and examining novel modes of production and consumption—all of which were directly influenced by Christina’s experience.

Figure 4. Craft makers, researchers, and local stakeholders in dialogue during the HEPHAESTUS co-creation workshop on Bornholm (September 2024). Photo: HEPHAESTUS Project (2024).

2.2.2 Synergies to T3.1

In Task 3.1 (T3.1), CBS art-based researchers Raffaella Rivi and Sergio Marchesini (WP3) have focused on speculative design and future-oriented thinking about the craft sector. By conducting field trips, workshops, and interviews, they explored how decentralized production, supported by digital and distributed technologies, can transform the craft-making profession. These activities, including the engagements with craft ambassadors and local communities on Bornholm and Dals Langed, have provided invaluable insights into how craft can contribute to sustainability, community development, and local economies. The goal was to envision how these ideas can be integrated into future craft practices that are socially and environmentally responsible.

These forward-looking explorations directly feed into T5.4, which aims to develop a roadmap for a socially sustainable circular economy through craft. One of the key activities and objectives of T5.4 is the organization of a think tank, where living lab participants—including craft-makers, designers, researchers, and all other key stakeholders—are invited to discuss the role of craft in shaping the future of the circular economy. The think tank explores several critical issues such as the potential of craft-makers to drive sustainable green tourism, local economic revitalization, and the creation of more sustainable experience economies. Through these discussions, the aim is to identify how decentralized craft production, informed by technological advancements, can strengthen local economies and ecosystems.

The ideas and insights generated from T3.1 will provide foundational material for the think tank's deliberations. For instance, the potential for digital technologies in craft-making—explored during the field visits and interviews—aligns directly with the discussions in T5.4 on how decentralized production can benefit local ecosystems. The experiences documented in T3.1, including workshops that explored civic craft and the reinstallation of exhibitions like *Brave New World* on Bornholm, offer concrete examples of how craft can evolve in a way that supports both sustainability and community engagement.

Moreover, T3.1's exploration of speculative futures, in line with futures design methodologies that emphasize the creation of immersive, participatory experiences to envision possible social and environmental outcomes (Candy & Dunagan, 2017), provides an opportunity for the think tank to address the social, economic, and environmental aspects of sustainability in a comprehensive way. By bringing together the ideas generated through T3.1 with the practical expertise of the participants, we can collectively refine the vision of craft as a driver for green economies and local revitalization. This vision has been explored in detail during the living lab activities, such as the co-creation workshop on Bornholm in September 2024.

The work of T3.1 also contributes to the think tank's goal of stimulating cross-sector collaborations. Through interviews and discussions with craft ambassadors and experts in production economics, the groundwork for future partnerships has been laid, and can be replicated and outlive the HEPHAESTUS Green living lab. These collaborations will be crucial as the project moves forward in testing innovative ideas and solutions within the green living lab framework (see D5.2).

3.0 Organizing the HEPHAESTUS Think Tank

This section describes the organizational structure and strategic operation of the HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank. It outlines how the think tank builds upon the established Maker’s Island network, highlights the integration of key stakeholders, and details its adaptive, collaborative governance model designed to ensure ongoing innovation and policy influence within the craft and sustainability sectors.

3.1 The HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank Going Forward

In line with the broader conceptualizations of think tanks outlined in Section 1.0—including their capacity to inform policy debates, foster collaboration, and drive innovation (Jezierska, 2020; Pautz, 2011; Wellstead & Howlett, 2021)—the HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank builds on the network and insights established through Maker’s Island Bornholm. As discussed in Section 1.1, the Think Tank is envisioned as a flexible, multi-stakeholder platform that unites policy, craft, academia, and industry to co-create sustainable futures for European craft ecosystems. In practice, this is operationalized with the HEPHAESTUS project formally entering into the Maker’s Island steering committee via BOFA’s representation herein.

3.1.1 Maker’s Island and the Formation of a Think Tank within the HEPHAESTUS Project

By linking Maker’s Island’s grassroots strengths to the EU Horizon Project HEPHAESTUS, this new Think Tank becomes a living embodiment of the “dynamic intermediary” model described earlier and illustrated in Figure 1. While Maker’s Island has proven its worth in mobilizing Bornholm’s craft identity, it now faces possible discontinuation due to shifting funding and political priorities. The HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank offers a path forward, allowing local actors to retain the collective knowledge, trust, and structural achievements that have been built thus far.

3.1.2 A Collaborative Think Tank for Innovation in Craft and Sustainability

Reflecting the evolution of think tanks as catalysts for transformative approaches (Rashid, 2013; Smith et al., 2013), the HEPHAESTUS Think Tank seeks to bring together experts from disparate domains—design, waste management, tourism, policy, and more—to address the needs and opportunities of European craft ecosystems. Specifically, it offers:

- *Consensus-Oriented Policy Engagement aligned with EU norms*
Ensuring that collaborative, multi-level governance frames the conversation around craft and sustainability.
- *Knowledge Mediation*
Bridging academic research with practitioner insights, continuing Maker’s Island’s mission of empowering local artisans to participate meaningfully in shaping policy and market opportunities.

3.1.3 Core Objectives of the Think Tank

Building on this foundation, the Think Tank centers its work around five interrelated goals:

- *Developing Sustainable Craft Models*
Championing circular-economy strategies, informed by BOFA’s “Bornholm without Waste 2032” efforts.
- *Bridging Traditional Craft and New Technologies*
Exploring how digital fabrication, eco-friendly processes, and other innovations can scale artisanal know-how.
- *Policy and Advocacy*
Engaging with policymakers across local, national, and EU contexts to secure resources, reduce barriers, and promote craft-friendly regulations.
- *Education and Skill Development*
Working with the Royal Danish Academy to update curricula and introduce new learning pathways for budding artisans and seasoned makers alike.
- *Economic and Cultural Impact Analysis*
In partnership with Destination Bornholm and Business Center Bornholm, measuring and boosting the sector’s viability and resilience.

3.1.4 Collaborative Structure and Network Governance

To remain both operationally robust and academically grounded (Ahmad, 2008; Pautz, 2020), the Think Tank harnesses expertise from a network of institutions that have already demonstrated strong collaborative impact through the Maker’s Island initiative (see Section 2.1.1). This includes regional policymakers, cultural institutions, business development actors, and sustainability experts.

Rather than relying on hierarchical structures, the Think Tank organizes its efforts through issue-based working groups and rotating convenings within the Maker’s Island steering committee. This flexible model ensures that partner roles remain adaptive to evolving opportunities—especially as the future of Maker’s Island’s central secretariat remains uncertain.

3.1.5 Interdisciplinary Collaboration and Long-Term Vision

Much like new-wave think tanks that collaborate with government and civil society (Rashid, 2013; Fraussen & Pattyn, 2023), the HEPHAESTUS platform is conceived as an ever-evolving structure. It convenes regular working groups, interdisciplinary research projects, and pilot interventions within the HGLL framework. Bornholm’s localized expertise thereby informs broader European discourses on sustainable craft, while international insights shape innovative local experiments in return.

Ultimately, by weaving together Maker’s Island’s established networks and the operational versatility characteristic of modern think tanks, the HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank positions Bornholm as a leader in craft-centered sustainability. This dual commitment – to grassroots engagement and forward-looking policy research – seeks to secure Bornholm’s World Craft Region legacy for generations to come.

3.1.6 Outputs and Next Steps

Despite uncertainties about Maker’s Island’s future, the Secretariat and its core collaborators remain committed to:

- *Developing a sustainable operational model*
Covering funding mechanisms, governance structures, and strategic roadmaps.
- *Supporting green tourism and the broader experience economy*
Through new projects and synergies.

- *Integrating BOFA within Maker’s Island’s remaining network*
Ensuring seamless collaboration on circular practices.

The Maker’s Island steering committee currently serves as the coordinating structure for the Think Tank, meeting approximately every two months with a rotating agenda that includes budget oversight, strategic coordination, and partner-led activity planning. The committee operates through a mix of formal agenda items and partner roundtables, allowing for both decision-making and shared updates across institutions. Key working themes—such as future organizational models, green tourism, and circular economy initiatives—are developed collaboratively within smaller task groups, with decisions and workstreams re-integrated into the wider steering group meetings. As of March 2025, with BOFA’s formal entry into the steering committee of Maker’s Island, BOFA has taken on a more central role, including hosting duties and continuing with budgetary contributions initiated in 2024, reflecting the Think Tank’s evolving scope and shared governance model.

3.2 The Bassano Ecosystem and its contribution to the Vision Think Tank

The Bassano ecosystem, which brings together key stakeholders such as the Municipality, Trade Union Associations, Academia, and other local ecosystems, plays a critical role in supporting the think tank’s objectives, particularly in the context of Task 1.3 and Task 3.1. These stakeholders contribute significantly to discussions on the future of craft in shaping the circular economy, social and economic development, and environmental sustainability within local communities. Figure 5 demonstrates the support network and system of the Bassano ecosystem.

Figure 5: Visualisation of the Bassano stakeholder support structure

3.2.1 Business Models for Craft Makers

In alignment with T1.3, which focuses on co-creating sustainable business models for craft makers, the Bassano stakeholders help shape the framework for redefining and strengthening the craft maker profession. The ongoing collaboration between local trade unions (CNA Vicenza and Confartigianato Vicenza), the Municipality, and academia (Cà Foscari and Roma Tor Vergata) facilitates key insights into the needs and challenges faced by craft makers, such as the integration of digital and distributed technologies, intellectual property rights, and sustainable production methods. These discussions feed directly into the think tank's mission to explore new business models and create sustainable ecosystems for craft makers.

The stakeholders in Bassano, with their active participation in local networks, provide essential data and insights for envisioning the future potential of craft in a circular economy. By being part of the think tank, the Bassano ecosystem will contribute to discussions on the decentralization of craft production and the role of craft makers in the emerging green economy and green tourism sector. This aligns directly with T3.1's exploration of future trends and innovations that push the boundaries of craft's role in revitalizing local economies and enabling sustainability.

3.2.2 Think Tank and HGLL Synergies

The think tank will make use of the input from stakeholders in the Bassano ecosystem to develop a roadmap for crafting a more sustainable, circular economy shaped by craft. Their collaboration highlights the potential for craft makers to be drivers of a sustainable experience economy. The Bassano Museums, as important local institutions, also serve as platforms for these discussions, offering spaces for craft makers to meet, engage, and increase visibility within the local community.

Further, stakeholders in the Bassano ecosystem will contribute to the vision of the think tank, by addressing topics such as decentralized production and sustainable business practices, linking these to local economic revitalization strategies. The integration of the Bassano ecosystem stakeholders ensures that the discussions held within the Bornholm green living lab will be informed by real-world insights and experiences from the Italian ecosystem. By combining these localized ecosystems, the think tank can catalyze cross-sector collaborations and initiate practical testing within the HEPHAESTUS green living lab on Bornholm. This collaboration forms part of a broader effort to develop a network that empowers and supports craft makers. Ultimately, the think tank aims to generate actionable insights that can influence the growth of a regional craft ecosystem based on sustainable principles, with implications for both local and transnational scale.

4.0 Towards a Road Map for Circular Economy

The HEPHAESTUS Vision Think Tank is currently shaping a roadmap that integrates the ongoing circularity efforts on Bornholm with the sustainable innovation initiatives described in previous sections. In light of the threats to Maker’s Island’s secretariat—along with BOFA’s entry into the steering committee – this roadmap will function as a pragmatic framework for advancing the craft sector’s resilience under uncertain conditions.

Rather than a distant planning document, the roadmap is being developed through active collaboration among BOFA, the Royal Danish Academy, Maker’s Island working groups, and other stakeholders engaged in the Living Lab. It will be documented and made available through appropriate channels, e.g. the HEPHAESTUS website under the HGLL sub-section (see: <https://hephaestuscraft.eu/living-lab/>). Each actor brings specific expertise: BOFA contributes circular-waste insights, the Royal Danish Academy supports competence development, and Maker’s Island participants highlight local challenges and best practices. The outcome is a present-focused guide that anchors immediate action while still envisioning long-term circular-economy transitions.

4.0.1 Focus Areas and Approaches

- *Sustainable Business Models*
The roadmap synthesizes pilot projects and proven practices that showcase viable paths to profitability under a zero-waste paradigm.
- *Lifelong Learning and Competence Development*
Training modules—offered through the Royal Danish Academy and local partners—expand craft makers’ skills in waste reuse, digital fabrication, and financial planning.
- *Organizational Cohesion and Trust-Building*
Ongoing engagement with craft makers addresses the communication gaps identified in Maker’s Island, ensuring transparent decision-making and inclusive agenda-setting.
- *Policy and Governance Alignment*
By coordinating with regional authorities, the Think Tank advocates for immediate policy support—from streamlined grant mechanisms to regulations favoring circular practices.
- *Knowledge Transfer and Replicability*
Collaborations with parallel ecosystems (like Bassano) feed into shared workshops and comparative research, ensuring that lessons learned can be applied beyond Bornholm.

4.0.2 Structure and Timeline

The Think Tank continuously compiles data from BOFA’s waste-management initiatives, Maker’s Island working-group reports, and academic insights provided by CBS and the Royal Danish Academy. This information is funneled into agile “roadmap updates,” which are shared periodically with all stakeholders. The process acknowledges immediate constraints—such as diminished municipal funding—and works within them by proposing short-term pilot actions while maintaining a vision for broader systemic change.

The Think Tank’s structure – depicted in Figure 1 (see Section 1.1)—visually conveys its position as a dynamic intermediary between the HGLL and Bornholm’s broader craft ecosystem. This structure underpins the roadmap’s development process by enabling horizontal collaboration between stakeholders, including BOFA, the Royal Danish Academy, and Maker’s Island working groups. Each partner feeds insights from local projects, policy deliberations, and training efforts directly into iterative roadmap updates, ensuring they are rooted in shared governance and operational flexibility.

4.0.3 Living Document for Present Realities

Crucially, the roadmap remains a living document. As BOFA takes an active role within the Maker's Island steering committee, new findings from each pilot or training session are systematically incorporated, refining both near-term measures and long-term strategic direction. This iterative format ensures that the roadmap is not merely reactive, but deliberately responsive—aligning dynamically with the craft sector's evolving needs and emerging challenges. It is poised to adapt as new circumstances, partnerships, or regional frameworks develop, thereby safeguarding the continuity of circular-economy transitions within Bornholm's creative industries.

As the future of Maker's Island's central infrastructure remains under discussion, contingency planning has also considered alternative institutional pathways for maintaining the Vision Think Tank's momentum. One such option – still exploratory – would involve anchoring the Think Tank as a research and engagement platform within Copenhagen Business School (CBS), the coordinating institution of the HEPHAESTUS project. A potential CBS-hosted Vision Think Tank could provide a neutral, research-driven space for long-term stakeholder engagement, capacity building, and policy advisory work – particularly if regional coordination capacities on Bornholm diminish. However, such a transition would require careful alignment with CBS's strategic direction and long-term funding commitments, and remains only one of several possible futures for the Think Tank's institutional anchoring.

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